

Short Communication Magnetochromatography

R. P. Shukla and L. M. Lall

Strain⁴ described the combination of chromatography and electrophoresis using two electrodes inserted in an alumina column. Columns packed with glass wool, asbestos fibre¹ or glass powders² have been employed for separating protein and their hydrolysates. The separation of amino acids and peptides on a paper strip moistened with a buffer was first described by Weiland *et al*⁵. Nobody seems to have applied magnetic field in a solenoid for the separation of ions in paper chromatography. The present work has been undertaken to see effect of magnetic field in a solenoid on R_f value in paper chromatography (developer used were the same as recommended by Lederer⁶).

The experiment was repeated thrice to see the reproducibility of results.

EXPERIMENTAL

The paper taken was Whatman No. 1 chromatographic supplied by M/s. W. and R. Balston Ltd., England while the chemicals used are either "Analar" or pronalysie of M/s. B.D.H. or S. Merck respectively which were redistilled. The strip was suspended in a

Fig. 1

1. J. A. V. Butler and J. M. L. Stephens, *Nature*, 1947, **160**, 469.
2. H. Haglund and A. Tiselius, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1950, **4**, 957.
3. F. H. Pollard, J. F. W. M. C. Orme and I. I. M. Elbein, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 466.
4. H. H. Strain, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 1292.
5. T. Weiland and E. Fischer, *Naturwiss.*, 1948, **35**,
6. E. Lederer and M. Lederer, *Chromatography*, Elsevier 1957, p. 493.

cylindrical jar of 5.2 cm. diameter and 36 cm. height around which was wound thin insulated copper wire carrying current. As a control one cylinder without applying magnetic field was taken and the R_f was determined in it also. Our results were within a limit of ± 0.04 unit variation from those of Pollard *et al.* The whole apparatus was kept in a thermostatic bath which was capable of maintaining temperature. Constant upto $\pm 0.018^\circ\text{C}$ no. of turns in the coil for the 1st and 2nd field respectively are 199 and 378. The current in both the cases was 1.35 Amp.

DISCUSSION

Normally when no field is applied many of the ions have the same or practically same R_f value, and are not separable, but they can easily be separated by applying magnetic field. Thus the R_f value as observed by Pollard and others³ for Al^{+++} and Ag^+ and repeated by the authors differ by only 0.06 but on applying a magnetic field of 337.73 gauss the difference in R_f value is 0.28 and at a field of 641.52 gauss it is 0.07.

RESULTS

TABLE I

Solvent 50% n-butanol; 35% Distilled water; 10% Glacial Acetic Acid; 5% Ethyl Aceto acetate.*

Sr. No.	Ions	R_f without Magnetic field	R_f with an applied field	
			337.73 gauss	641.52 gauss
1.	Ag^+	0.12	0.81	0.81
2.	Al^{+++}	0.18	0.53	0.91
3.	Cr^{+++}	0.66	0.52	0.80
4.	Pb^{++}	0.19	0.08	0.08
5.	Ba^{++}	0.17	0.16	0.07
6.	Mg^{++}	0.21	0.13	0.15
7.	Ni^{++}	0.26	0.22	0.39
8.	Co^{++}	0.26	0.31	0.87
9.	Mn^{++}	0.24	0.64	0.87
10.	Sr^{++}	0.20	0.61	0.86
11.	Cd^{++}	0.30	0.68	0.74
12.	Sb^{+++}	0.17	0.90	0.93
13.	Ca^{++}	0.21	0.79	0.96
14.	Cu^{++}	0.68	0.79	0.83
15.	Sn^{++++}	0.19	0.99	0.99
16.	As^{+++}	0.18	0.95	0.95
17.	Hg^{++}	0.88	0.93	0.96
18.	Zn^{++}	0.33	0.98	0.99
19.	Bi^{+++}	0.36	0.99	0.99
20.	Fe^{++}	0.75	0.98	0.99

Similarly in case of Pb^{++} and Ba^{++} the difference in R_f value changes from 0.02 to 0.08 and 0.01 respectively.

The differences in R_f values under magnetic field of the other ions which are better separated in a magnetic field are tabulated below along with the differences in R_f values as observed by authors,

TABLE II

Sr. No.	Ions	Difference in R_f without field	Difference with fields	
			337.73 gauss	641.52 gauss
1.	Mg ⁺⁺ —Pb ⁺⁺	0.02	0.05	0.07
2.	Co ⁺⁺ —Ni ⁺⁺	0.00	0.09	0.48
3.	Cd ⁺⁺ —Sb ⁺⁺⁺	0.13	0.22	0.19
4.	Cd ⁺⁺ —Ca ⁺⁺	0.09	0.11	0.22
5.	Sn ⁺⁺⁺ —As ⁺⁺⁺	0.01	0.04	0.04
6.	Fe ⁺⁺ —Cr ⁺⁺⁺	0.09	0.46	0.19

Thus it will be observed from the above data that a better separation can be achieved by applying magnetic field.

However, when it was tried to relate these results to magnetic properties of ions no theoretical relation could be obtained. Further work on higher magnetic field and other organic molecules is in progress and will be published later which may, perhaps, give a relation with magnetic properties of ions.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
GOVERNMENT COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
RAIPUR, M. P.

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